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**PROMOTING SCIENTIFIC RESEARCHES OF IHE SCIENTISTS:
COMPREHENSIVE SOLUTIONS**

Objective. One of the main tasks of the University Library today is to create a new additional effective virtual environment for research activities - its own open access electronic information resources. The work is aimed at considering virtual communication forms of representing scientific achievements of researchers of the National Technical University “Kharkiv Polytechnic Institute” (NTU “KhPI”) in various fields of science, production and industry. **Methods.** Using the example of specific bio bibliographic scientific projects (schools), which are being developed in KhPI Scientific and Technical Library, a comprehensive approach to their realization is considered. **Results.** Due to a comprehensive approach, the concept of information integration was first implemented – the electronic resources of the Library site, the University repository and electronic and paper versions of the journal were combined. **Conclusions.** Only through joint efforts of scientists and librarians can we promote and disseminate the results of university research in the modern scientific and educational space and raise the ranking and image of our university among higher education institutions of Ukraine and the world.

Keywords: KhPI scientific schools; promotion of scientist's achievements; scientist's bio-bibliography; own electronic resources

Introduction

The University's intellectual center has always been the Library, which follows new visions and accumulates the strategy of developing the scientific communication environment. Thanks to the productivity of cooperation between the University and the Library, we can present in any form and format the directions of scientists' activities and their world discoveries in science and technology.

One of the main tasks for today is to create a new additional effective virtual environment for research activities - own open access electronic information resources. It is more appropriate for libraries to focus their resources on enhancing electronic content in the open space, presenting materials on the history of the university, promoting the scientific achievements of its community, scientific schools and information about their founders and bright representatives (Semenenko, & Poberezhna, 2017), which enhances the image of the university, informs the scientific community of Ukraine about the achievements of NTU “KhPI” scientists, their significant contribution to the development of scientific schools. It is the availability of free access to full-text resources that significantly improves the training of higher education institutions, makes education more accessible, and the diversity of forms of presentation of scientific achievements increases the interest of users.

Methods

The Scientific and Technical Library of National Technical University “KhPI” develops several bio-bibliographic scientific projects (schools) related to the formation, development and world recognition of NTU “KhPI” – “Scientific School of Electrical Engineering”, “Scientific School of Chemistry”, “Rectors (Directors) KhPI” and “Scientists of NTU “KhPI” – education, science, industry: the best editions». The advantage of projects is a comprehensive approach to their implementation.

Project objectives:

- popularization of the influence of scientific achievements of NTU “KhPI” on the formation and development of a specific industry;
- increasing the accessibility of the achievements of the best polytechnic scientists by enhancing the presence of their scientific publications in the electronic information environment;
- lend-out increase of documents from the collection «Publication of scientists of NTU “KhPI”»;
- restoration and compilation of the bibliography of NTU “KhPI” scientists.

Results and Discussion

Thanks to a comprehensive approach, the concept of information integration was first implemented – the electronic resources of the library site, the University repository and electronic and paper versions of the journal were combined. Project Summary:

- the maximum list of publications of scientists / directors / rectors has been revealed;
- historical materials are presented in the form of a series of virtual exhibitions,
- at virtual exhibitions information about life and scientific activity, photos, bibliography of works of a scientist and about him/her with references to electronic versions of the main texts is presented;
- electronic versions of the full texts of the main articles from scientific journals are included in the scientific circulation (as evidenced by the statistics of text downloads);
- texts are scanned, full texts of publications are placed in the institutional repository;
- bibliographic records in virtual exhibitions have links to electronic versions of the full text of articles (placed in the collection “History of NTU “KhPI” in the institutional repository eNTUKhPIIR - <http://repository.kpi.kharkov.ua/>);
- creative design of the color page of the journal focuses on the main works of a scientist and the direction of his/her activity (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Color page of “Energy Saving. Power engineering. Energy audit”

The publications of the past years are introduced into the scientific circulation, historical facts about scientists are presented on the basis of primary sources and archival information; the availability of this section in paper and electronic versions of the journal has increased the number of users.

The concept of the project «Scientists of NTU “KhPI” – education, science, industry: the best editions» was developed in 2015 and 87 publications of scientific achievements of scientists have already been presented according to the results of the competition of the university «Best editions of NTU “KhPI” (Kostromina, 2016, November 30). The material about the publications and the authors is presented on the site of the Scientific and Technical Library in the form of the page section «Scientists of NTU “KhPI” – education, science, industry: the best publications» (Fig. 2) according to the scheme:

Освіта

- Абітурієнтам
- Студентам
- Організаторам навчального процесу

Наука

- Конференції, семінари
- Дисертації, автореферати
- Наукометричні дослідження

Проекти

- Учені НТУ «ХПІ» – освіти, науки, промисловості: кращі видання
- Ректори (директори) НТУ «ХПІ» [ХПТІ, ХТІ, ХХТІ, ХММІ, ХЕТІ, ХПІ]
- Наукова школа електротехніки ХПІ

Головна » Учені НТУ «ХПІ» — освіти, науці, промисловості: кращі видання

Учені НТУ «ХПІ» — освіти, науці, промисловості: кращі видання

НАВЧОВА БІБЛІОТЕКА НТУ «ХПІ» **Про проект**

Екологічно стайлий розвиток міст

Екологічески устойчивое развитие городов : учеб. пособие / Н. Н. Самойленко, В. Б. Байрачный, В. П. Шаповров, А. Каклаускас, Е. В. Кофанова ; Нац. техн. ун-т «Харьковский политехнический ин-т». — Харьков : Щедра садиба плюс, 2015. — 220 с. : табл., рис. — Електронний аналог печатного издания в репозитарии НТУ «ХПІ».

Анотація

Русский

Поділитися...

Figure 2. Page of the section “Scientists of NTU “KhPI” – education, science, industry: best publications” on the site of the scientific and technical library of NTU”KhPI’

- bibliographic description of the publication, cover,
- extended edition abstract,
- the content of the publication,
- reviews or responses to the edition (if any),
- information about the authors:
 - photo of the author;
 - surname, first name and ORCID (if any);
 - date and place of birth, family relations with famous artists, scientists, public figures;
 - the position occupied by the author;
 - education with the name of the higher education institution;
 - scientific degree, rank and indication of the year of receipt;

- Honorary titles, awards with indication of the year and the name of the awarding institution);
- Academic title and year of receipt;
- a brief description of the activities in the institutions where he/she worked, which positions he/she held; basic directions of scientific researches.

□ GoogleScholar profile link (if available).

The projects have received awards at various competitions: “Scientific School of Electrical Engineering” as a result of the competition “Librarian of the Year 2015” (the organizer is the methodical association of libraries of higher educational institutions of Kharkiv region and LLC “PAER”) employees of STL NTU “KhPI” received diplomas of the competition «Librarian of the Year» in the nomination «For the creation of own electronic information resources» and diploma of the participant of the third regional competition of scientific works and innovative projects named after L. B. Khavkina “Libraries, Their Organization and Technology”.

“Scientists of NTU KhPI – education, science, industry: best publications” according to the competition «Librarian of the Year 2016» (the organizer is the methodical association of libraries of higher educational institutions of Kharkiv region and LLC “PAER”) employees of STL NTU “KhPI” received the diplomas «Librarian of the Year» in the nomination «For the creation of own electronic information resources».

Conclusions

It is due to joint efforts of scientists and librarians that we can help to activate and popularize scientists, professors, researchers of our university in the modern scientific and educational space and raise the ranking positions and image of our university among higher education institutions of Ukraine and the world.

Library staff are ready to join in ordering the bibliographic and full-text data sets, cataloging them, forming the databases for further integration of their own generation resources into the national system. We strive to come up with new ideas; support the e-learning system based on the concept of openness, develop an environment conducive to research and learning, providing qualitative service and information support, creating a comfortable space in the library, creating an interesting and comfortable virtual space (Semenenko, 2018).

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ПОПУЛЯРИЗАЦІЯ НАУКОВОГО ДОРОБКУ ВЧЕНИХ ЗВО: КОМПЛЕКСНІ РІШЕННЯ

Мета. Одним з головних завдань університетської бібліотеки на сьогодні є створення нового додаткового ефективного віртуального середовища для науково-дослідницької діяльності – власні електронні інформаційні ресурси відкритого доступу. Робота спрямована на розгляд віртуальних комунікаційних форм представлення наукових здобутків учених Національного технічного університету “Харківський політехнічний інститут” (НТУ “ХПІ”) у різних галузях науки, виробництва та промисловості. **Методика.** На прикладі конкретних біобібліографічних наукових проєктів (шкіл), що розвиваються у науково-технічній бібліотеці “ХПІ”, розглянуто комплексний підхід до їх реалізації. **Результати.** Завдяки комплексному підходу вперше реалізовано концепцію інтеграції інформації – поєднано електронні ресурси сайту бібліотеки, репозитарію Університету й електронної та паперової версії журналу. **Висновки.** Тільки спільними зусиллями вчених і бібліотекарів можна сприяти активізації та популяризації результатів досліджень ЗВО в сучасному науково-освітньому просторі й підвищувати рейтингові позиції й імідж університету серед закладів вищої освіти України та світу.

Ключові слова: наукові школи ХПІ; популяризація доробку вченого; біобібліографія вченого; власні електронні ресурси